

SOCIAL SCIENCES

CONTEXTUAL ANALYSIS OF PROVIDING STUDENT-PERSONAL EMOTIONAL STABILITY DURING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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КОНТЕКСТНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ ЛИЧНОСТИ СТУДЕНТА В ХОДЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОГО ПРОЦЕССА

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Abstract

The article highlights the theoretical components of attention to the important aspects of the implementation of tasks, such as the correction of negative situations such as various deviant situations observed among students studying in higher education institutions, tendency to aggression, laziness and lying, failure to learn subjects on time. Also, in the article, the practical importance of establishing the cooperation of psychologists+parents+educational institutions in ensuring the emotional stability of the student, in the rational use of individual characteristics, in the formation of emotional state regulation skills, was explained based on theoretical conclusions.

Аннотация

В статье выделены теоретические составляющие внимания к важным аспектам выполнения заданий, таким как коррекция таких негативных ситуаций, как различные девиантные ситуации, наблюдаемые у студентов, обучающихся в высших учебных заведениях, склонность к агрессии, лени и лжи, неуспеваемость, учить предметы вовремя. Также в статье выявлена практическая значимость налаживания взаимодействия психологов-родителей-образовательной организации в обеспечении эмоциональной устойчивости учащегося, в рациональном использовании индивидуальных особенностей, в формировании компетенции регуляции эмоционального состояния и объясняется на основе теоретических выводов.

Keywords: emotion, emotional stability, psychoemotional, psychogeometric test, student-personality, psychodynamic model, experimental.

Ключевые слова: эмоция, эмоциональная устойчивость, психоэмоциональность, психогометрический тест, личность студента, психодинамическая модель, эксперимент.

Introduction

Based on the dynamics of socio-political, cultural and economic processes taking place in society and the influence of the human factor, various events that take place in domestic and social life affect the psycho-emotional state of a person at different levels. In return, socially disapproved or approved behavior patterns and various psychological states are expressed. According to the information of the International Health Organization, 45% of patients who turn to hospital doctors are considered healthy people who only seek to correct their emotional state and get rid of negative emotions [18, p. 5]. It is for this reason that the issues of ensuring the emotional stability of a person under the influence of various factors of the external environment, including the student, the rational use of individual characteristics, and the formation of the skills of emotional state

regulation are an urgent issue in the focus of psychologists. After all, various deviant conditions observed among students studying in higher education institutions, tendency to aggression, laziness and lying, failure to learn subjects [22, 23, 24, 25, 26] on time are among them.

The object of the study. In accordance with the requirements for psychological research, the educational activity of 70 students was selected as a means of developing emotional stability.

The process of forming the emotional stability of the student's personality and ensuring its improvement during the educational process was chosen as the subject of the research.

The purpose of the research is to study the uniqueness of the formation of emotional stability in the student through educational activities and determine the conditions for improving emotional stability.

Analysis of literature on the subject

Any incidents, conflict situations, crises, frustration, stress, etc. that occur during the educational process place high demands on the student's personal resources. The issue of ensuring psycho-emotional stability, taking into account age, ethno-cultural and regional characteristics, from foreign scientists J.P. Tangney, K.W. Fisher [1], Russian scientists L. Kitaev-Smyk, E. Zharikov, Ya. Reykovsky, V. Dolgova [6, 7, 10, 16], studied separately in the scientific works of Uzbek scientists E. Goziev [20, 21], G. Shoumarov, V. Kariyeva, Z. Nishanova and others [9, 13].

The issue of ensuring psycho-emotional stability is considered an actual scientific-psychological topic, and L. Abolin studied the mechanism of human emotional stability. He stated that "in ensuring emotional stability, it is necessary to take into account the role of individual psychological characteristics, as well as the role of a person's life experience and the situation" [2]. L. Gozman paid special attention to the role of emotions in the relationship system and studied the level of their influence on the functional state of a person based on practical experiences [5]. The work of L. Gozman can be used as a methodical source in studying the psychology of family relations.

Some aspects of this topic are A. Rasulov ("Study of the individual-psychological characteristics of a person using a psychogeometric test" [15] and "Personality study tests and their requirements") [14], Z. Nishanova, Z. Kurbonova, S. Abdiev and Sh. Tolaganovas ("Psychodiagnostics") [13] studied by.

However, in the above-mentioned scientific researches, the contextual analysis of ensuring student-personal emotional stability during the educational process was not carried out.

Analysis and results

Emotions (lat. *Emovere* - to excite, excite) - the main category of mental processes and situations related to instinct, need, motive, reflected in the form of direct experiences (satisfaction, joy, fear, sadness, etc.), affecting the world and activity of an individual [12]. Emotions appear in the process of evolution as a means of determining the biological essence of external influences and the state of the organism, and show different appearances depending on their psychological characteristics and the law of expression. Emotion also performs a number of tasks in providing a person with a spiritual life. O. Badulina in his scientific work "Педагогические основы эмоционального благополучия дошкольников" showed that the emotional stability of preschoolers is manifested in the family environment, the role of fathers and mothers, and the nature of the relationships of other children in the family with family members [3]. The results of this scientific work carried out on the basis of experimental experiments are intended to be used in the activities of the employees of psychological service rooms of pre-school educational institutions, that is, to be used practically in ensuring

the psychological development of school-aged children.

It is said that emotions are the process of direct forgiveness of this or that feeling by a person (including the student-J.N.,N.N.). [5] For a perfect person, the fact that he occupies his position in the system of social relations and spends his life evokes a positive emotion. Therefore, studying the student's emotional sphere, determining the method of its correction serves to ensure the effectiveness of psychological support activities. From the point of view of practical psychological services, I. Voropaeva's work entitled "Correction of emotional sphere of a young school student" has a special meaning; the author presents the technique of psychological correction, the method of establishing a professional relationship between the psychological helper and the recipient of psychological help.

It is known from the history of psychology that several theories about emotion have been created. For example, Ch. Darwin created the evolutionary theory of emotions. According to him, emotions are either useful or a rudiment (residue) of reactions that appeared in the process of evolution in order to fight for life. An angry person blushes, breathes heavily, and clenches his fists. This requires active muscle contraction, vigorous breathing, and blood circulation that keep the muscles working. Moreover, he explained the sweating of the hands from fear by the fact that it was easier for primitive people to grab its branches so that they could climb up the tree in case of danger.

The psychodynamic model of emotion is based on the theories of Z. Freud, who in his theories indicated two types of the emergence and manifestation of anxiety, anxiety:

a) alarming anxiety appears as a reaction to awareness of a clear external danger;

b) traumatic anxiety develops under the influence of an unconscious, internal source, and the suppression of inclinations and aggressive instincts is a vivid example of the cause of this type of anxiety.

According to James-Lange's Peripheral Theory of Emotions, emotions are associated with specific physiological reactions. For example, a person who sees a predator runs away in fear. Nevertheless, there should also be a change in the body, that is, when a person is afraid, the body trembles. The origin of emotion is expressed as follows: an influencing factor → the occurrence of a physiological change → these changes are reported to the brain → an emotion appears.

The study of the emotional state is directly related to the issue of ensuring psychological health, L. Tarabakina in the scientific work entitled "Эмоциональное здоровье школьника: теория и практика психологического сопровождения" studied the level of practical significance of psychological observation in ensuring psychological development based on experimental experiments. In the opinion of the author, "assigning the results of observation of schoolchildren to the Psychological map ensures the purposeful determination of psychotechniques used for the organization of psychological work carried out at school, to ensure individual psychological development" [19, p.70].

It is known from the sources studied within the topic that the study of the emotional state has its own history as a scientific problem, its study in the science of psychology can be divided into several groups, and each group, in turn, is likely to be divided into separate parts. These are:

In the scientific works of the first group, it can be shown that the emotional state of preschoolers has been studied.

In the second group of scientific works, the emotional state of school-aged people was studied.

In the third group of scientific works, it can be shown that the emotional state of high school students has been studied.

In the fourth group of scientific works, it is possible to point out the studies of the emotional state of teenagers [8].

In the scientific works of the fifth group, it is possible to show the scientific works in which the emotional state of academic lyceum and technical school students was studied [4].

It can be pointed out that the emotional state of students of higher educational institutions was studied in scientific works of the sixth group [17, 18].

It is noted that emotional stability is manifested as a topical social issue during adolescence. 90 % of high school students are in a state of emotional tension, and 75% have a disease of stress etiology [11].

The psychological components of ensuring the emotional stability of the student are determined by the following conditions:

- firstly, the factors affecting the formation of the emotional stability of the student personality in the higher education system have not been defined. Identifying them serves to improve educational conditions;

- secondly, it serves to study the educational conditions for the formation of emotional stability in the student, to improve the existing processes;

- thirdly, the data obtained on the basis of empirical research serve to improve the approaches to determine the current psychoemotional state of students, and the obtained results can be used in the operation of the "Psychological service room", etc.

Conclusion and suggestions

For this reason, the need and demand for scientific and practical research on improving the techniques and technology of working with students and youth of psychologists working in higher educational institutions is increasing. The reasons can be explained as follows:

Firstly, almost all higher education institutions are located in urban centers, which causes some inconvenience for students studying from rural areas (distance from parents, blood relatives, accommodation problem, unfamiliar city, etc.). These situations, in turn, lead to a struggle within the student's personality (why is he unique, why am I not unique, etc.). Due to the unique interpersonal relations in the urban and rural social life, serious changes occur in the personality of the student. After all, a student from a village will first have to adapt to the conditions of the city. The same process is observed in the educational activity, it is necessary to adapt to the conditions that are new for the student in

the form of traditions and values formed in the institution of higher education, mentor-student relationship, and it is in such a complex process that the emotional stability of the student's personality becomes of practical importance. In this process, it is appropriate to establish cooperative relations in the higher education system in the form of "psychologist + tutor + responsible for youth issues, spiritual and educational affairs + professors + teachers + parents = ensuring a positive course of student adaptation";

Secondly, in the higher education system, the student encounters subjects that are "foreign" to him. Because of this, he faces difficulties in mastering these "foreign" subjects. This, in turn, has a negative impact on the formation of professional qualities expressed in the personality of the student. As a result, the student "refuses" to study and master subjects that seem difficult to him. This represents the emotional instability of the student's personality. Of course, the professional skills of science teachers are important for the positive progress of this process. For this reason, raising the quality level of the pedagogues working in the higher education system, paying serious attention to the issue of retraining and improving their qualifications, allows to achieve positive results;

Thirdly, it is manifested in mastering the teacher-student relationship formed in a higher educational institution. In this case, the student faces the process of "unfamiliar relations" and his unwillingness to participate in this process causes him some discomfort. For example, an older teacher addressing him as "You" or younger teachers adding suffixes such as "khan, jon, oy" to his name will make him "angry". Emotionally stable students quickly adapt to this relationship and quickly learn this norm. Emotionally unstable students are the opposite. In this process, he may argue with teachers and create conflict situations. It is precisely in these X situations that any student feels the need for psychological services. Unfortunately, if we take into account that qualified psychologists and psychological service centers that respond to such services are "rare" in most higher education institutions, the practical importance of ensuring the psychological stability of the student becomes stronger. For this reason, it is recommended to establish specially equipped psychological rooms in all higher educational institutions and to establish a system of encouraging their work by hiring qualified and competent psychologists.

References

1. Williams R.M. Values // Ed. E. Sill. International encyclopedia of the social sciences. – N.Y.: Mac, Millan, 1968. – P. 283 – 287.
2. Аболин Л.М. Психологические механизмы эмоциональной устойчивости человека. – Казань: Казанский университет, 1987.
3. Бадулина О.И. Педагогические основы эмоционального благополучия дошкольников // Дисс. кандидата пед... наук. - М.: 1998. – 125 с.
4. Буслаева М. Ю. Психолого-педагогические условия формирования эмоциональной устойчиво-

сти студентов педагогического колледжа // Диссертация кандидата психологических наук. – Челябинск, 2009.

5. Гозман Л.Я. Психология эмоциональных отношений. – М.: Изд-во Моск. ун-та. 1987.

6. Долгова, В.И. Формирование эмоциональной устойчивости личности // В.И.Долгова, А.А.Напримеров, Я.В. Латюшин. – СПб.: РГПУ им. А.И.Герцена, 2002. – 167 с.

7. Жариков Е.С. Психологические средства стрессоустойчивости. – М.: Московский кадровый центр, 1990.

8. Идобаева О.А. Исследование эмоционального благополучия современных подростков как предпосылка коррекционной работы школьного психолога // Дисс...канд. психол... наук. – М.: 1998. – 143 с.

9. Каримова В. Ижтимоий психология. Дарслик. – Т.: Фан ва технология, 2012. – 172 б.

10. Китаев-Смык Л. А. Психология стресса. – М., 1980.

11. Копина О.С., Сулова Е.А., Заикин Е.В. Экспресс-диагностика психоэмоционального напряжения и его источников // Ж. Вопросы психологии. – 1995. №3.

12. Мещеряков Б. Г., Зинченко В. П. Большой психологический словарь. – М., 2002.

13. Нишанова З., Курбонова З., Абдиев С. ва Тўлаганова Ш. Психодиагностика. – Т.: 2008.

14. Расулов А. “Шахсни ўрганиш тестлари ва уларга қўйиладиган талаблар” // Ж. Мактаб ва ҳаёт. 2009. 1-сон.

15. Расулов А. “Шахсининг индивидуал-психологик хусусиятларини психогеоетрик тест ёрдамида ўрганиш” // Ж. Касб-хунар таълими. 2007, 6-сон.

16. Рейковский Я. Экспериментальная психология эмоций. – М.: Прогресс, 1979.

17. Рокицкая Ю. А. Развитие адаптационного потенциала эмоциональной устойчивости в профессиональном самоопределении студентов // Диссертация кандидата психологических наук. – Екатеринбург: Уральский государственный педагогический университет, 2010.

18. Сары-Гузель В. Р. Оптимизация эмоциональной устойчивости личности студента через учебную деятельность // Диссертация кандидата психологических наук. – Нижний Новгород, 2002.

19. Тарабакина Л.В. Эмоциональное здоровье школьника: теория и практика психологического сопровождения // Дис... доктора психол... наук. – Н - Новгород, 2000. – С. 70.

20. Ғозиев Э. Умумий психология. – Тошкент 2002. 157-бет.

21. Самаров, Р. (2014). ЭРГАШ ҒОЗИЕВНИНГ “ПСИХОЛОГИЯ МЕТОДОЛОГИЯСИ” ЎҚУВ ҚЎЛЛАНМАСИ–ФАН СОҲАСИ РИВОЖИГА ҚЎШИЛГАН МУҲИМ ҲИССА (Профессор Эргаш Ғозиевнинг “Психология методологияси” ўқув қўлланмасига тақриз). Современное образование (Узбекистан), (2), 66-68.

22. Рахронов, Д. А., & Назарова, Н. Ж. (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ПЕДАГОГИК ХОДИМЛАРНИНГ ҲУҚУҚИЙ МАҚОМИНИ БЕЛГИЛАШНИНГ ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛ АСОСЛАРИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(TSTU Conference 2), 377-384.

23. Abdusalamovna, A. S., & Juraevna, N. N. (2022). A Strong Family as a Determining Development of Society. International Journal of Development and Public Policy, 2(6), 31-36.

24. Жуманиязова, Н. С. (2019). СОВРЕМЕННАЯ СИСТЕМА ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ: ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ И ПРОПОРЦИОНАЛЬНОСТЬ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ПРОЦЕССОВ. Экономика и социум, (11), 261-263.

25. Хусенов, Н., Хонимкул, С., Нурмаматов, Т., & Маткаримова, Ж. Д. ВОПРОСЫ АКТИВИЗАЦИИ УЧАСТИЯ МОЛОДЕЖИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА В ЖИЗНИ ГРАЖДАНСКОГО ОБЩЕСТВА. Zbiór artykułów naukowych recenzowanych., 36.

26. Маткаримова, Ж. Д. (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИДА НОДАВЛАТ ИЖТИМОЙ ИНСТИТУТЛАРНИНГ КАДРЛАР БАНДЛИГИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШДАГИ ИШТИРОКИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(TSTU Conference 1), 297-303.